

Effects of Principals' Leadership Styles on Teachers' Performance at Secondary Schools in Dera Ismail Khan

- Farhat Yasmin** Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Management Sciences, Qurtuba University of Science and Information Technology. D.I.Khan KP. Pakistan. Email: Zamir16ahmed@gmail.com
- Muhammad Imran** Assistant Professor, Department of Management Sciences, Qurtuba University of Science and Information Technology. D.I.Khan KP. Pakistan.
- Maria Sultana** Assistant Professor, Department of Management Sciences, Leads University, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

Abstract *This learning was directed acts discover the effect of Principals leadership strategies on teachers' act of secondary school in D.I.Khan. The research was cross sectional and parametric in nature. The record was collected by both from principals and teachers of secondary school located in the district. The outcomes were fascinatingly opposing to the assumed statements i.e in this broadsheet the impact of transactional and transformational guidance style has been found contrary on teachers' enactment. The reason for such phenomena has been deliberated in this broadsheet. The study concluded that both leadership styles i.e transformational and transactional styles of principles of the school understudy have been found not supporting in improvement in teacher's performance.*

Key Words

Transformational Leadership,
Transactional Leadership,
Teachers Performance.
Secondary School

Introduction

In previous times, principals were only required to administrate and to have political skills. On the other hand in present times, various other guidance strategies and professional tactics are also needed from the principals. The truth unmasks the real picture of school's principles duties that beside the instructional and influencing behavior, now in modern days principals are allocating with many other responsibilities like administration, financial drops, school's security, data handling and advertising etc. Consequently, beside with actual administrative controlling qualities, principals in modern time need to possess Facts and various skills added with administrative culture and management. In the past the character of the principal was merely a source of motivation for teacher's efforts in teaching process and that might lead towards fruitful outcomes but in this period the character is promptly changing with passage of time. In present studies the trend has been changed according to which principal's guidance is the utmost desire for the success of students in academic race.

Principal has a vital character for teachers to play in facilitating operative leadership in secondary schools. In this regard that the efforts and the efficiency of the teachers enactment in school was not up to the mark due to insufficient leadership elegance of the principal. The concept of leadership was observed in Many different geographical locations of the world along with different organizational arrangements. Around 55% of civil servants are employed in education sector in KPK, From 0.18 Million civil employees, one-third of the teachers belong to Elementary and Secondary Education section. Further enhancement in this sector by making employment each year by KPK Govt, more teachers have been employed in ESE, KPK. Many administrative units have been established to make education sector reformed to avoid hurdles due to bureaucratic procedures. Such units will boot up interest of teachers in education. (Rahim, 2016).

Literature Review

The variations and differences in leadership styles exist due to change in institutional administration and management structures with respect to different geographical locations. This was the actual and basic reason behind the existence of different managerial styles within a similar type of educational field and environment. It was there for a primary need of every principal that there

should be a possibility of smooth running of all institutional activities and all the work directions should be clear to all the fellow members so that the required objectives and targets should be accomplished and achieved in better way.

Chandan (1987) contributed to support this point by saying that leadership grace and effective style is an important element of an individual personality that is embodied in a leader which makes his/her subordinates to follow him/her. Leadership style is a precise enactment that a leader assumes in order to inspire and encourage the subordinates therefore the objectives and goals of the institute can be accomplished professionally and successfully. It is the systematic approach which was adopted by the school principals in order to achieve institutional objectives (Adeyemi, 2006).

Therefore the ability of the principal's operating and administrating is based on the performance of the front-runner. Attitude plays a significant role in the selection of specific styles for specific organizational purposes (Douglas, 1996). Due to current global drifts towards gaining and achieving fame in education, a scorching debate has formed a changed nature of leadership talents and skills according to which a school teacher, as well as principal and panels of management, should be practiced and settled in to achieve high educational quality output by operative employment of prospectus. School management is the main pillar of our education system. Diversity of glitches has been confronted and overcome by supervisors on daily basis. Each and every school supervisor trails his own educational management idea that encompasses a diversity of features that helps him to solve and handle multiple problems on daily basis. The word leadership himself replicates the influential, enthusiastic folks by whom winning armies have been absorbed, well-off and vigorous empires have been built or the classification of nations have been transformed.

In the past, the principal's role was to encourage teachers in their teaching efforts that contributed to making desirable results, however, the tendency nowadays has been changing fastly (Lashway, 2003). This paper is in the direction to discuss and cover a wide extent of role of principal's leadership in making student's success ratio better and improved. At secondary school as such that of higher education level, the role of principal is not less important to provide effectiveness of teachers and students in school environment. Alageheban (1997) elaborated the effectiveness and efficiency staff performance is highly Influential by the style of leadership of Principal. Reliably, the literature advocates the prominence of role in educational sector played by leadership style of principles for better and efficient performance of the institute, staff, and students as well. (Al-Omari, 2008; Dimmock, 2003; Simkins, 2003). Leadership's significance for education sector is universally accepted important often times but sometimes this seems to be only single option that determines the success and failure of any educational institute whether college, university or school (Simkins, 2005). The importance and need for the improvement of educational leadership have been accepted and thrown light by many studies (Bush and Middlewood, 2005). The burning issue for quality improvement in education has given rise the importance and nature of leadership styles. The researches have dated and proved that leadership styles have impact on teachers' performance and good quality education as well as good curriculum (Ibrahim & Orodho, 2014). For individual's development, leadership has been taken as an elementary factor for human development of educational sector and performance of the school, therefore, various leadership programs, globally have increased (Northhosue, 2010b). Leadership as a term reflects an individual having energetic and powerful command over his armies, who has been built effective empire and has changed nation's course. All such refers to the importance of leadership toward an educational institute. (Yukl, 2002). So that it is believed that not only the difference is made by a leader but he tends others to understand what are his plans. Among the most important elements, leadership is highly important element toward success and or failure of any institution (Bass, 1990). Taking it from different angles, it is diverse comprehensive element among other stakeholders who are responsible for school performance. Among crucial and critical factors, leadership style of principals is very important in any educational setting, this proves the influence of leadership on school development (Whitaker, 1997). Many schools try to make distinguished efficiency and only such schools are able to show difference in students' achievement and learning capacity whose principals contribute more actively than other schools (Hallinger & Heck, 1998; Smith et al, 2001).

Managerial skills and leadership style are considered the most significant components for bringing enhancement in school management and ultimate to education's quality. The school principal is the most focal, authoritative proficient who's ultimately responsible for improvement in school management and professional leadership by delivering his administrative services to a school (Armstrong, 2004). Numerous studies have investigated the basic connection of leadership styles such as autocratic and democratic among teachers and how student's achievements are affected by these styles. Current literature equipped in this scenario also recommends these styles by investigating that student's academic achievements are directly affected by the style of school leaders (Ross & Gray, 2006). Authority is given to employees according to approach of Laissez-faire leadership means a workplace should be provided to them where they can freely perform their work without the intervention of anyone

but then anyway research has demonstrated that following such leadership style has been proven the least satisfying and least effected management style.

The key features of coaching leadership are the teaching and supervision of the followers and for improvement required in performance are just because of the considerable care and attention of sensible leaders. Worker's skills can be flourished to a boom level by following this approach and to achieve that superlative level of performance, coaching leadership initiates and encourages the followers. The current study focuses on defining and answering the question which defines "an effective school" and an effective principal is considered one of the most common attributes. It was presumed by scholars and researchers that job satisfaction for teachers has a direct linkage with principal style and eventually the indirect effect on the student's academic accomplishments with the principle style. Conscious studies finally concluded that student's basic skills of achievement have been considerably affected by the induced competencies of great school leaders (Leithwood, Begley, & Cousins, 1992). In the same vein studies upshots opposite results such as Kruger, Witziers, and Slegers (2007), by proposing that don not rely more on leadership that it is the only feature effecting the student's outcomes, rather it influences but indirectly on institutional differences and culture.

Transformational management tactic transforms individuals and social systems by providing guidance about conveying fluctuations in establishments, sets, oneself and others. Life-changing front-runner inspires more to achieve unpredicted or extraordinary outcomes. When satisfactory teaching given to the employees, life-changing front-runners bounce self-sufficiency to the employees over a precise work as well the right of making choices. Mostly other stimulating hopes are set by them for the followers and they usually perform better presentations with the help of this. Transformational style of leadership has focused that the involvement of workers where the head of organization is not one dominant person, instead he permits his subordinates individuals to join in choice making in explaining that what should be prepared to achieve countless educational responsibilities or coursework and how it can be made successful with the combine consent and contribution of all employees. The involvement of workers doesn't reflect that management is having deficiencies or lacking administrative quality of making decisions but it was the most operative way to stimulate the workers toward numerous responsibilities of the organization and also to get multiple options and choices(Obama et al., 2015). The transactional manner could be termed as the conservative style as most of the decisions were retained by the upper management of the institutions and the followers were only instructed to follow the orders regardless of their opinions. Heads of the institute become careless in taking the review of their followers or in observance of work-related behavior and attitude. The leader was only interested in getting objectives of the tasks (Dubrin, 2007).

Therefore, based on the literature review, the following hypothesis is developed;-

H₀₁: Principals' transformational management grace meaningfully and absolutely affects teachers' enactment in secondary schools of district Dera Ismail Khan.

H₀₂: Principals' transferable guidance elegance affects teachers' enactment in secondary schools of district Dera Ismail Khan.

Methodology

The study was showed quantitatively by allocating modified and altered surveys to the battered population of this specific research. The very attractive and significant attribute of quantitative method was that it provides the scholar with facility to generalize the findings recorded from small sample on the entire population (Hagan, 2006). It also confers the previous study of Fink (2003) and Hagan (2006) which demonstrates that to take the snapshot about population's generalizability; the quantitative approach facilitates the researchers in this concern by grouping the sample in small groups for conducting survey. Neale et al (2005) argued the statement from Stenner and Martin (2004) which says that when the objective of the study is to get reproduction and general then instead of using qualitative techniques study should use quantitative techniques. Consequently, quantitative methodology is considered the most fitted to complete this specific research with the hope that it will contribute to the generalization of the finding to the larger population which is attained from this survey.

Population, Sample and Data Collection

The current study targeted the population of 33 schools that permitted to collect the data from its employees and to distribute the questionnaire. Among these schools the population consisted of all the teaching faculty of these government schools. So through the convenience sampling method all the available faculty was questioned through questionnaire to collect the relevant data. The main objective of sampling is to get the data and information from the small but accurate representative portion of the population and then to generalize the findings on whole population. A total of 353 questionnaires returned and among them 300 questionnaires were properly filled and used for further analysis.

Instrument

The question items regarding transformational and transactional leadership styles were taken from Bass and Avolio's (1995) inventory of 36 items, where 20 items were related to transformational leadership while remaining 12 items were related to transactional leadership style. Teacher performance was measured using 14 items. The Cronbach's alpha value of leadership styles and teachers' performance was above .7.

Data Screening and Analysis Procedure.

The collected data was entered into IBM SPSS-24. The database was screened out for the normality of the data. The Skewness and Kurtosis values were below ± 3 . So, the data was further processed to run demographic attributive results and simple regression to catch the consequence of transformational and transactional guidance grace on teachers' enactment.

Findings

There were 225 female respondents and 75 male respondents. Most of the teachers/principals fall under the service tenure of 06-10 years those were 134 followed by 81 respondents having tenure of 11-15.

Hypothesis.

H1: Principals' transformational guidance graces knowingly and definitely disturbs teacher's enactment in secondary schools of district DIKhan.

The simple regression was run to catch the positive significant conclusion of transformation guidance grace on teacher presentation. The coefficient of determination was .05 which shows a 05% share in change in teacher performance due to transformational leadership style. The F-value was $<.05$ which proved the model significant statistically. The result of regression is given below;-

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	5.726	.154		37.074	.000
Transf L	-.225	.055	-.229	-4.061	.000

The identical constant of regression $b = -.229$ is important but forecasts damagingly the teachers' enactment, The improved modification in one unit in life-changing guidance grace carries .229 unit decrease teachers enactment. So, the hypothesis H2 is rejected.

Hypothesis 2:

H₂: Principals' transactional management grace disturbs momentous confidently teachers' act of secondary schools of district DIKhan.

The R^2 was .023 which showed that the contribution of the transactional leadership style was very low in changing teachers' performance. Though the model was statistically significant at $P < .05$. The simple regression result was run to catch the predictive influence of principals' transactional guidance grace on teachers' enactment.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	5.551	.167		33.294	.000
Trans L	-.165	.062	-.153	-2.670	.008

The uniform constant of regression $b = -.153$ is important to forecast the transferable guidance result on teachers' enactment but harmfully inclining to worthless assumption. The rise in one unit in transferable guidance grace carries .15 unit reduction in teachers' enactment. Thus, grounded on the momentous $P < .05$ adverse forecast, H₂ is rejected.

Argument and Recommendations

Here is the lone technique of information gathering was cast-off in this research. And such technique was based on investigation surveys. The whole of the gadgets are assumed from the preceding research, moreover the formalities, consistencies, and rationalities are well described in the preceding research. In this research information is usual through skewness and kurtosis; all the standards of skewness and kurtosis are in the variety as stated by Field (2013). The basic objective of this paper was to find the influence of leadership styles on teachers' performance in the context of district D.I.Khan. It was well-known that transformational guidance and transactional guidance exhibited modification upon enactment, but the consequence initiates undesirable as $b = -.229$ and $-.153$, correspondingly. These outcomes illustrate that Bass and Avolio's (2002) model is defensible separate the native learning situations wherever study accompanied, but not in the limited situation. Outcomes might be undesirable because of some other influences that were not sheltered in this research like legislative policies, the individual's behavior of the Leaders, legislative organization, teachers relations, etc. it is recommended that education department can use effective leadership styles to increase the performance of teachers.

It is therefore suggested that the quality of guidance strategies can be improved in the scholastic set at secondary schooling level that would be suitable and helpful for enhancing and polishing the performance of teachers. It can also be recommended that policy for education in Pakistan must use and adopt new multiple guidance techniques. Mutually, qualitative as well as the quantitative technique of examination will result in more reliable outcomes in stint of creating judgment over both the approaches in forthcoming studies. Forthcoming studies may discover the restraining aspects which would enhance or improve the track of affiliation among guidance methods and instructors' presentation. To increase the teacher's performance it is correspondingly recommended that different other leadership styles should be followed for education by policymakers in Pakistan.

References

- Adeyeme, T.O. (2006). *Fundamentals of Educational Management*. Lagos: Atlantic Associated Publishers.
- Avolio, B.J. & Bass, B.M. (1995). Individual Consideration viewed at multiple levels of analysis: A multi-level framework for examining the diffusion of transformational leadership. *Leadership Quarterly*, 6, 199-2018.
- Chandan, J. S. (1987). *Management theory and practice*. New York; Vikas Publishing
- Douglas, D. (1996). The Ethics of Managing People. *A European Review*, 5(3).
- Dubrin, A.J. (2007). *Leadership Research Findings, Practice, and Skills*, (5the.d.). Boston.
- Hagan, F.E.(2006). Organized Crime.Trends in Organized Crime.9(4).
- Lashway, L. (2003). Distributed Leadership, *Research Roundup*, 19(4).
- Obama, M. O., Eunice, L. A., &Orodho, J. A. (2015).Effect of Principals' Leadership Styles on Students' Academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Homa-Bay County, Kenya.*IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*.Vol. 20, Issue 3, pp. 51-60
- Okumbe, J.A. (1998). *Educational Management: Theory and Practice*. Nairobi University Press: Kenya.
- Yukl, G. (2002). *Leadership in Organizations*.University of Albany, New York, Pearson Publishers.